

Fugitive Frames: Nomadic semiotics in image analysis

Los marcos fugitivos: Semiótica nómada en el análisis de imágenes

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Abstract

The history of visual sociology is geographically and temporally dispersed to such a degree that it can be difficult to perceive as a coherent sociological area of study. Add various past cultural and political movements in sociology more broadly, and entire periods of development can be rendered invisible. This article will briefly review some pivotal moments in the Anglo-American record of visual sociology to show how the question of analysis and more specifically image analysis is underdeveloped. By considering the debates in the field, and by looking at the origins and trajectories of possible approaches, we will outline a nomadic semiotic approach using the lens of a specific case study to focus on some essential characteristics and sociological repercussions of the approach in question.

Keywords

Image Analysis, semiotics, nomadism, visual, politics.

Resumen

La historia de la sociología visual está tan dispersa geográfica y temporalmente que puede resultar difícil percibirla como un área de estudio sociológico coherente. Si a esto se añaden los diversos movimientos culturales y políticos del pasado en la sociología en general, períodos enteros de desarrollo pueden resultar invisibles. Este artículo repasará brevemente algunos momentos cruciales en la trayectoria angloamericana de la sociología visual para mostrar cómo la cuestión del análisis, y más concretamente del análisis de imágenes, está poco desarrollada. Teniendo en cuenta los debates en este campo y examinando los orígenes y la trayectoria de los posibles enfoques, esbozaremos un enfoque semiótico nómada utilizando la lente de un estudio de caso específico para cen-

trarnos en algunas características esenciales y repercusiones sociológicas del enfoque en cuestión.

Palabras clave

Análisis de imágenes, semiótica, nomadismo, visual, política.

To challenge the regimes of representation that govern a society is to conceive of how a Politics can transform reality. As this creative struggle moves onward, It is bound to recompose subjectivity and praxis. More often than not, it requires that one leave the realms of the known, And take oneself there where one does not expect, is not expected to be.

Trinh T. Minh-Ha, *When the Moon Waxes Red*

1. Introducción

Implicitly or explicitly, sociology has been perennially concerned with representation. Whether it be the depiction of narratives from interviews, ethnographic fieldwork, the style of quantitative data in tables or graphs, or even the question of the researcher and the nature of observation itself, ocular and aesthetic practices are woven into sociological work. Even so, precise attention to the work of visibility, visual representational practices, and images, has periodically surfaced in limited stretches of scholarly history in sociology. In the epigraph, filmmaker and postcolonial theorist, Trinh T. Minh-Ha, provides an eloquent point of reference for thinking with the epistemological commitments required when taking images seriously, the transformational nature of human understanding, the risks, and rewards.

Attending to the visual, to images, or to visibility per se, means challenging regimes of representation and interrogating conventional and formulaic or standardizing approaches to research both on the practical level of approaches and methods, as well as the level of demonstration of results. Additionally, a shift to a relational paradigm is necessary to produce an analysis within a transversal space across analog and digital registers, and other binary constructions. This article invites readers to explore the limits of “the realms of the known” Minh-Ha refers to above through the displacement (praxis vis-à-vis dialectical space) necessary to destabilize the “other” from the sphere of knowledge as something subject to acquisition or mastery. Part of this involves resisting tendencies toward the instrumentalization of methodology and reliance on “systems of binary opposition (subject/object; I/It; We/They)” (Minh-Ha, 1991: 12). We will begin with an historical excavation of some key moments in the history of Anglo-American visual sociology, and then operationalize of the notion of image in order to discuss the work of semiotics vis-à-vis visibility and the dimension of nomadism. Having laid a foundation, we will build an analysis of the phenomenon of the upside-down ostensibly red equilateral triangle image/symbol (▼) that has reached such notoriety that it has been banned in Germany and censored on social media platforms like Facebook. Through the process of that case study, we will be able to work through the limitations and affordances of the analytical techniques offered by the proposed methods of nomadic semiotics.

2. Histories Interrupted

Over 40 years ago in an early article for *Qualitative Sociology*, California-based sociologist Clarice Stasz (1979) discussed the “operation of conventions, which...

appear problematic” (p. 29) in displaying photographically based research. Along with other USA sociologists like Jon Rieger, John Grady and Douglas Harper, who had either studied visual sociology under Howard Becker, drawn from his work or made their own advancements, the standards for visual presentation of work like photographs were seen as issues that could impact “sampling, reliability and validity” (p. 29). The concern with legitimacy when working with visual materials, was –and is to this day– interlaced with a disciplinary iconoclasm that crosses a broad range of areas in the social sciences and humanities, as WTJ Mitchell’s (1984) calls for interpretive vigilance show. The scientific leaning of sociology in the USA taking root in the late 1970s and still exerting influence today was due partly to “sociology’s image of itself as a science and theory driven discipline and its correspondingly restricted view of what constitutes acceptable analytic practice” (Grady, 1991: 23). Over the decades, various sociologists (Grady, 1991; Cheatwood and Stasz, 1979; Becker, 1995; Harper, 2000; Guggenheim, 2013, 2015) have lamented the resistance to, or lack of serious attention to visual culture or visual methods whereby the “‘Visual’ is considered to be strange, not really sociology, not really scientific, or it is simply forgotten” (Guggenheim, 2013, online)¹. In today’s image saturated world with seemingly endless proliferation of digital and symbolic forms, more and more sociologists are turning to the question of the visual.

Stasz (1979) bemoaned sociology’s lacunae in using the visual when compared to the traditions evident in anthropology (p. 32), and the lack of standards or discernment strategies for knowing when images were used more sociologically than artistically or journalistically, coupled with a lack of guidance or criteria for the use of captions and attending to image/text relations. She identified 3 main issues:

- Historical: “Unlike anthropology, sociology has no history of the visual ethnography. Description in sociological ethnography comes from words, not images” (p. 32).
- Researcher Role/Position: “Most sociologists write in the passive voice and avoid reference to themselves as active agents... Overall, the observer or reporter in sociological papers is to be bland in personality and unconnected to the world outside the observed setting” (p. 32).
- Analytical: “Barthes offers a framework for examining the relationships between text and images. Essentially, he offers categories to guide such analysis, not the analysis itself” (p. 31).

Before moving to methodological and, more specifically, analytical concerns, it is important to first briefly address historical and researcher positionality issues. Historically, Stasz’s 1979 claim that visual ethnography was non-existent in the discipline’s tradition was incorrect, but the truth was obfuscated thanks to political and cultural biases. When conducting archival research within early volumes of the *American Journal of Sociology* for another article published around the same time, Stasz discovered that “you will find something virtually unseen in sociology journals of recent decades—photographs” (121). Reviewing journal issues from 1896 to 1916 revealed “244 photographs as illustrations and evidence” (*ibid.*), an abundance of visuals that had completely disappeared by the 1920s. The marginalization of researchers using image-based research, suggested to her that early 20th century sociology’s distancing from images might be due to narrow ideas of what being

¹ For an in-depth discussion of these historical debates and contexts, please see Cambre, C. 2021. “Visual Sociology.” In *The Palgrave Handbook of Image Studies*, edited by Krešimir Purgar, 735-757 (Ch. 45). Palgrave MacMillan.

“scientific” meant. This attitude was manifested, for example, in the arguments of the journal’s editor Albion Small for a focus on statistics.

Eclipsing the omission of early visual sociology published in the USA prior to the 1920s, was an even greater gap resulting from “a logic of segregation [that] shaped all aspects of American society, including American sociology” (Collins 2007: 576): In short, the marginalization of Black scholarship. A white Euro-centric gaze led sociology in the USA to promote of the Chicago School as the first US school of sociology, despite evidence that it was predated by the Du Bois led Atlanta Sociological Laboratory. Having conducted in-depth ethnographic studies in the 1890’s that entailed over 5,000 interviews (King 1968, reprinted in Foner 1970: 14), Du Bois mobilized his research in combination with census data to create an award-winning exhibition for the 1900 Paris World Fair that provided compelling social insights using visual data and images created with a team of graduate students.

Effecting one of the earliest scholarly examinations of the social through and by images, W. E. B. Du Bois, arguably the first visual sociologist, showed the realities of racism and how it impacted the lives and opportunities of Black communities to powerfully counter prevailing narratives of inferiority.

Du Bois wrote: “The bulk of the exhibit is an attempt to picture present conditions. Thirty-two charts, 500 photographs, and numerous maps and plans form the basis of this exhibit [...]” (576). The Exposition Report noted: “It is impossible to do justice to this exhibit in a few lines of descriptive matter. The material presented was not only of high scientific value but was shown in the most graphic way” (vol. 2, 408-9). He displayed the photographs and infographics (or data portraits) in the award-winning Paris exhibition with three thick albums of hundreds of photographs, and two sets of infographics. Through curation, the albums, which contained no captions, pushed viewers to reframe how they were looking at the contents. The data visualizations of sociological statistics induced viewers to de-automate their tacit perceptions, spurring them to newly rethink the information. The various parts of the exhibition referenced each other to build an internally rich and coherent research argument (Cambre 2021: 750).

Figure 1

WEB Du Bois. Paris Exhibition 1900 (digital file from original) LC-USZ62-132752 (b&w film copy neg.)
Library of Congress [Public Domain]

Given the sophistication, and impact of the rigorous work Du Bois showcased over 100 years ago, it is almost certain that other work will have been overlooked or sidelined in historical records. More archival work and better practices of grounding visual sociological antecedents are warranted, but for our purposes here, we can assert that a robust, underexplored tradition exists, and merits consideration moving forward.

The second issue troubling Stazs (1979) can be summed up as one of researcher reliability and plagues empirical work to this day but is more exacerbated in visual sociological work because images demand an added layer for researcher placement. Unlike the practices of the 1970s, today's leading journals endorse the use of statements where researchers declare their positionality (e.g. declaring one is part of the community being investigated, or that one is using a feminist or critical framework). No longer is the ethnographer's presence unstated, and today's readers can gauge the possible embodied ways researchers might impact participants. Additionally, biographical indications allow readers to understand the personal or political lenses a researcher might implicitly engage, unlike Levi-Strauss's presentation of the solitary ethnographer in *Tristes Tropiques* (1974) even while his wife was alongside helping collect data (Stazs, 1979). While a relational paradigm requires researchers to account for subjectivity in their practices, for visual work, revealing field contexts and conceptual/epistemological commitments do not go far enough.

When engaging in either image production, collection/curation or analysis, the declared macro framework can be articulated with micro-level analysis (e.g., visual semiotics, socio-semiotics, visual rhetoric, iconology, visual discourse analysis) in reliable and transparent ways. Yet, a researcher's own perceptual tendencies are implicated regardless of whether the study focuses on depicted representations, their production or consumption, the conventions of style, or the uses of various visuals and the discourses surrounding them. Every image produced or analyzed invokes a point of view (how the gaze is situated), since "a depiction is never just an illustration [...] it is the site for the construction of social difference" (Fyfe and Law, 1988: 1). Images call for an added scholarly practice of including the affective and aesthetic responses of the researcher, because they operate on the register of the virtual – real but not concrete – or "the psychological, remembered and ideological aspects of the event of experience—diverse visual processes which are also articulated with the operations of power and governance" (Shields, 2004: 2). Why complicate matters in these ways? Why does *visual* sociological research require added attention to the relationships between the visible and perception?

In part, the answer lies within the ontological status of images themselves. Some of the prevalent approaches in social research involving images treat them as texts to be read, yet these approaches can only be reductive, and often end up atomistically dismembering images to fit various discursive models and their interpretive strategies. Generally, images are first viewed holistically, as surfaces, there is no preset sequence for the eye to follow while looking: the eye becomes a nomad, it can wander. Philosopher Vilém Flusser (2000) describes encountering images as surfaces where time and space function differently from texts that require readers to follow a sentence's linear progression to the end in what epitomizes a "historical consciousness" (p. 127). By contrast, the almost instantaneous grasp of an image summons a necessarily non-linear "imaginative consciousness" (p. 127). Who can deny that only a "naïve observer will tacitly assume that he can see the world through photographs...[which] implies that the world of photographs is congruent with the world 'out there'" (Flusser 2000: 29). This aspect of images and how it influences ocular and affective responses not only

constitutes an added layer to address through elaborating the conceptual status attributed to images, but also demands a paradigm shift on the part of the researcher.

Visual research need not endorse a monolithic or universal image theory, yet an articulation of the ontological/epistemological assumptions being made with regards to images serves to ground an analysis more robustly. One early philosopher who was exceptionally adept at this practice, and who is consistently invoked whenever scholarly image analysis is undertaken is none other than Roland Barthes. What can be learned from the ways Barthes approached images that traditional semiotic analysis has not fully addressed or incorporated? Turning to Stasz's (1979) third concern, that of the analytical framework, where she protests Barthes' presentation of guides for analysis but not the analysis itself, invites us to review some possible image theory frameworks before turning to the fundamental characteristics of a nomadic semiotics through which the case study can take place.

3. Frameworks of Analysis and Theories of the Image

As mentioned above, images are not subject to the confines of written or formal verbal communication (Schratz & Steiner-Löffler, 2003), but rather create space for complex ideas to be presented more directly (and paradoxically at times also more obscurely) than spoken or written forms of communication. Image interpretation is grounded in the exercise of examining the experiences of creating and perceiving pictures without treating sets of relations between their symbolic affordances and their potential meanings as closed systems. Prosser (2003) notes that "Images are, by their nature, ambiguous and do not in themselves convey meanings which are supplied serendipitally by those who perceive them" (p. 98). As such, it is useful to operate within a theoretical understanding of images that contemplates them as social interfaces, and accordingly position the research as something working with, through and perhaps by images: This task is challenging given that image theory is characterized by its refusal to be contained in any single field or discipline, which then generates hosts of overlapping terminologies and theoretical and methodological repertoires.

It follows then, that sociologists have the choice of drawing from frameworks offered across disciplines and combining them as needed. Hans Belting's work on the anthropology of images, for instance, builds on his conviction that "people's beliefs, superstitions, hopes and fears in handling images (2005) are what makes them manifest. For Belting (2005) an image *happens*, it "*may live in a work of art, but it does not coincide with it.*" (42). And thus, "images (are something that) happen between we who look at them, and their media, with which they respond to our gaze. They rely on two symbolic acts that each involves our living body: the act of fabrication and the act of perception, the latter the purpose of the former" (46). For the work of analysis, he proposes a tripartite interrelation where image, body and medium comprise the three poles (Belting, 2011). In art history, Georges Didi-Huberman (2004) theorizes visual figuration by distinguishing between what he calls the visual, the visible, and the virtual. One of the approaches introduced in sociology can be found in Rob Shields' (2004) six forms of visualicity (gaze/glance/ focus/depth/figure/ground) or Harun Farocki's "operational images" those which "do not represent an object, but rather are part of an operation" (Grønstad & Vågnes 2019: 79). Philosophy, beyond Barthes' concepts of punctum, studium, and myth (or anchor and relay) offers approaches like Merleau-Ponty's four layers of the invisible, that take phenomenological priorities. As this brief list shows, abundant frameworks for image analysis exist that can be mobilized for sociological analysis. However, the determination of the ontological and

epistemological status of “image” in any given study will obviously determine the framework/s employed.

Barthes remains one of the most cited writers on photography providing many scholars with points of traction for analysis. *Camera Lucida* written shortly before his death, can be seen as part of a progression in his thinking about photography, moving away from more structuralist essays like “The Photographic Message” (1961), “Rhetoric of the Image” (1964), and “The Third Meaning” (1971). The fluid structuring he provides in this book reflects an understanding that consciousness is always transitive, relational and in motion. Since he tries to rupture binaries and characterizes his approach by focusing on changeability and movement, it is no surprise that he would not provide an analysis but rather the “guides” that Stasz (1979) complains of. In a similar vein, Didi-Huberman (2004) calls for understanding images in ways that do not yet presuppose the figured figure, (as representational object), but only the *figuring figure*. Barthes enacts precisely this when he demonstrates what the punctum, or the “fugitive testimony” of photographs is for him. He looks at photographs and writes captions reflecting what it was that struck him, what came to mind, what accident “wounds” or “pricks.” him visually. For example, when describing the famous picture of a young Robert Mapplethorpe, Barthes is taken by the position of the figure and the expression of the face, but it is the hand that expresses for him an intensity of detail that compels him to caption it “...*The hand at the right degree of openness the right density of abandonment...*” (p. 63), with the ellipses at both ends, ragged unfinished and evoking the beyond of the punctum. It is critical to note that the kinds of things that flash into but rather those that lead his eye or disturb him are not those explanatory functions- such as to inform, to represent, to surprise, to cause to signify, to provoke desire.

Though literature on representation acknowledges the gap with reality, it is the moment of a viewer’s interpretation that serves to momentarily join representation and reality. The act of “seeing” is none other than the *not-synthesis* of an instance that is itself torn, rent, between consciousness and unconsciousness. Barthes (1981) sees it as a matter of co-presence (p. 42) and aesthetic appeal is secondary to the “injection of energy into the world” (Zivkovic, 2006 personal communication). The action of the punctum, then, is something that is both fully and completely visible and yet also fully and completely invisible. Du Bois’s 1900 exhibition, replete with photographs, pictures, records, and what are now known as infographics reflected an understanding that viewers would find themselves confronted, over and over, with a wide variety of visual content that they had never seen before, that contested their long held taken for granted notions of, for example, Black poverty in the southern states of the USA. Yet the exhibition overwhelmed them with images of Black prosperity, education, and economic and social success in a construction designed to create precisely moments of non-synthesis where narratives would rupture to allow for the possibilities of *other* realities. While Du Bois did not theorize the image explicitly, the use of visuality in his work demonstrates an understanding like that I have described above.

Researchers may take images as “things and non-things” (Mondzain, 2009) as event (Belting, 2005), as “immaterial physicality” (Jagodzinski, 2022) meaning a force relation following Deleuze’s Bergsonian approach. There are innumerable ways to conceptualize images, so that precisely because of this slipperiness, it becomes important to the analysis for a study to have a theory of the image with which to operate explicitly and ground the work. If researchers “pose problems and open meaning possibilities that take the visual manifestations of relationships as a central concern... [then] visuality becomes a gateway for presenting relationships that cannot be grasped

in any other way, because images demand to be understood on their own terms” (Cambre 2023: 200). For the purposes of the following case, images are characterized by mobility (changeability), performativity (agentic) and as atypical, or “unclassifiable, of a ceaselessly unforeseen originality” (Barthes 1975, 1979: 34) and as such, existing in the register of the virtual (Shields, 2003).

Images inhabit a volatile and catalogue of cognitive indecipherabilities that Alfred Gell says enchant beholders (the Du Bois exhibition for example) by frustrating their ability “to recognize “wholes and parts, continuity and discontinuity, synchrony and succession” (Gell 1998: 95) simultaneously. In sum, the image works as an interface between what is, and what is possible. If we accept the process philosophy position elaborated in great detail by Alfred North Whitehead that the social, “is a way of describing how each entity is constituted by and through its environment” (Halewood 2011: 121), then the sociological view entails thinking of images as “assemblages of movements and affective vibrations” (Jagodzinski, 2015: 514) that signal ““It is no longer form that is of interest, but a new hyletics—that is, the study of affect and percept” (Jagodzinski, 2015: 514) following Deleuze and Guattari’s propositions. Thus, we are no longer concerned with representation, *as such*: Instead, the focus becomes the “mutual constitution of entangled agencies...[whereby] distinct agencies do not precede, but rather emerge through, their intra-action” (Barad, 2007: 33). Traditional semiotic approaches then, are insufficient as British anthropologist Alfred Gell (1998) demonstrated in his magnum opus *Art and Agency: An anthropological theory*. Building from the concepts of index and abduction developed by Charles Saunders Peirce’s (1985) in his semiotic theory, Gell (1998) works through multiple empirical examples to demonstrate the roles of art and agency. Combined with this we will operationalize the notion of the virtual (Shields, 2003) to examine the inverted red triangle in what we can understand as a nomadic semiotics.

4. Nomadic semiotics: and the role of ‘artifice’ in a dynamic framework

Semiotics is “centrally concerned with reception”; in fact, its object is to describe the “conventions and conceptual operations” shaping what viewers do; “...it will not provide or even discover a meaning but will describe the logic according to which meanings are engendered” (Bal & Bryson, 1991: 186). In other words, the simplistic style of analysis that seeks to find the “meaning” of something is not the investigative goal because it is impossible to standardize the reception of a work [an image, text, object, etc]. As Walter Benjamin (1985 [1968]) reminds us in *The task of the translator*:

Not only is any reference to a certain public or its representatives misleading, but even the concept of an “ideal” receiver is detrimental in the theoretical consideration of art, since all it posits is the existence and nature of man as such. No poem is intended for the reader, no picture for the beholder, no symphony for the listener. ... For what does a literary work “say”? What does it communicate? It “tells” very little to those who understand it. Its essential quality is not statement or the imparting of information (p. 69).

The innumerable ways an image might be received by hosts of viewers moves analysis towards a dynamic view of the sign. Following the principle of “intra-action” (Barad, 2007), and C.S. Peirce’s definition of meaning as “the translation of a sign into another system of signs” (Eco, 1976: 1464), the process to be described involves viewers being constructed by the act of viewing at the very moment their viewing is also constructing what they see. It is helpful to keep this dynamic in mind, as well as

well as some ideas underlying C.S. Peirce’s inquiry that semiotician Roma Jakobson (1976) sums up as the problem of the role of symbols in our creative life. To address this, Jakobson would elaborate the concept of “artifice” in a lecture demonstrating relationships between signifiers and what they signify (Preziosi 2003, 143). Donald Preziosi (2003) takes up Jakobson’s work on the artifice and explains it shows the workings of how *adaequatio* or approximation, a tending toward, an as-if. Thus, this is not a “representation” as such, but a movement towards something.

Preziosi (2003) writes:

An iconic sign relationship (all these terms refer to relationships between things, not kinds of things) is primarily one of factual or literal similarity; an artifice(i)al sign is one of imputed similarity, of adequation rather than equality... I have been drawn to this notion of artifice in no small measure because it allows us to deal with the extraordinary complexities –the fluid and open-ended relativities– of visual meaning in a clear yet nonreductive manner (p. 146).

While many scholars mention the three principle sign types (icon, index, and symbol) C.S. Peirce developed in his formal doctrine, we follow Preziosi, and by extension Jakobson in considering a 4th main type, where the artifice operates. Each offers a different relation to the object and a different process of semiosis, however they are not mutually exclusive and a particular image may move between them in different iterations as well. Peirce’s initial distinction among three relations between signans and signatum, (Peirce 1931: 1558) is:

- An indexical relation based on factual contiguity;
- An iconic relation based on factual similarity;
- A symbolic relation based on imputed contiguity.

But Jakobson adds a fourth where the interplay of contiguity/similarity and factual/imputed, suggest the possibility of imputed similarity (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Sign relationships

	<i>contiguity</i>	<i>Similarity</i>
<i>factual</i>	index	Icon
<i>imputed</i>	symbol	Artifice

Artifice is performative and operates on the register of the virtual (because what we ‘see’ is other than what we are being shown, though we also see that) and intrinsically ambiguous, while it represents through a parallelism, represents by showing something that it is not to talk about the thing that it is. The virtual is key to understanding the workings of imputed signs. “The dictionary definition of ‘virtual’ was penned by none other than Charles Sanders Peirce.” (Skagestad, 1998: 2) For Levinson, “Peirce defines a ‘virtual’ X as what you get when the information structure of X is detached from its physical structure” (Skagestad, 1998: 2).

5. Case Study: The ▼ Red Triangle Pointed Down

A Canadian environmental activist posted a photograph of a simple tattoo on the outside of his right calf (Figure 3). A red equilateral triangle resting on one of its points rather than flatly on one side. Why this? Why here? Why now? The historical, cultural

and political contexts of sociological image analysis are highly complex. Many of the debates, issues and theoretical paradoxes gestured towards above deserve much more detailed and thorough exegesis. However, the literature presented here shows that concerns around images and analysis have merited much sophisticated theory building thus far. Building on some of these as starting points then, a nomadic semiotics of the image is best demonstrated through a case study, and in this instance, that of the red equilateral triangle pointed down (▼). The following sub-sections briefly present, or report on a) political contexts and usage; b) historical and cultural aspects before engaging in a critical pathway for a nomadic semiotics to build a foundation for the analysis.

Figure 3. Facebook post by M. Stainsby (2025, with permission)

5.1. Political contexts and usage

In July 2024, Germany's House of Representatives voted to ban the symbolic use of red triangles in connection to the Al-Qassam Brigades a military wing of the Hamas group (ASB Zeitung) and their use in pro-Palestinian media. Recently META (Facebook) and Instagram have also been censoring the use of the symbol online. Many countries classify Hamas as a terrorist organization, while Palestinians and those who endorse an idea of Palestine resistance, see Hamas members as resistance fighters. The highly fraught context around the ▼ is not only connected to its use in the ongoing conflict but also to the use of a red triangle to designate political prisoners under Germany's Nazi regime. People graffiti the image on walls, protesters give out stickers for individuals to leave on urban surfaces like windows and metro stations, or inside grocery stores. It is used on posters, flags, and finally, in this case study, as a tattoo (Figure 3).

Online, the Al-Qassam Brigades most frequently use it in videos where it is bobbing up and down over what they indicate to viewers as their targets, be it a tank or enemy soldiers: it functions as an arrow. Indeed, if one had only been exposed to these battlefield videos, the symbolic value does not exceed that of an arrow (see Figure 3).

The Al-Qassam Brigades have incorporated the ▼ into their logos, banners, and posters in specific and allusive ways, which has bi-directionally linked their digital material with that of organizations such as Free Palestine TV, who also include the ▼ into their logo. Figure 4 below shows 6 examples from the multitude circulating throughout the Internet gesturing toward a more formal use of the inverted red triangle after the bodycam videos of battle scenes became a viral phenomenon. Al-Qassam Brigade

videos begin with the ▼ under the script designating the term “ambush” and the Free Palestine TV channel uses a similarly positioned triangle over a green and a white, the colors of the Palestinian flag.

Figure 4. Triangles as arrows pointing to tanks or armored troop carriers (Video stills, Cambre 2024)

The triangle is used as part of Arabic script (meaning ambush) and also as an arrow pointing to further script in a military video showing an archer with the indigenous made weaponry. The Al-Qassam videos also use the image as part of highly allusive and complex visual narrative building by featuring the triangle “as-if” a signpost in different contexts on digital posters. Sometimes they refer to Israeli checkpoints or military ammunition but subvert what this would mean to Palestinians. After the death of Hamas political and military leader Yahya Sinwar in October 2024, the triangle appears as the foundation for his profile image, connecting the man to the movement visually. Unpacking each of these images in depth is beyond the scope of this paper, but they act as context for mapping the inverted red triangle's appearances.

Figure 5. Formal uses of the triangle online (Collected screenshots, Cambre 2024)

Both the extensive online use of the ▼image, and its offline use have contributed to the controversy over the image. Stickers simply featuring the inverted red triangle without any text, on transparent backgrounds have been handed out at pro-Palestinian protest marches in various places. These can then be applied in any number of situations, such as grocery stores to point to Israeli produce, suggesting shoppers (who identify and accord with the image) boycott a particular item. The stickers allow those holding them to become part of a wider participatory activity around the image that takes it offline. The activities can then be photographed, and the image moves back online when the user posts it. The oscillatory movement corresponds with the nomadic quality of the image. Sometimes the image can be taken to violent and destructive ends (Figure 8).

The “triangle has been sprayed on several venues, including a techno club and a bar” in Berlin (Gregson, 2024). On the “Combat Anti-Semitism” Facebook page, a post about the defacement of a building where the Chief Operating Officer of Columbia University in the USA was shared describing a red triangle painted on the wall and linking the image to Palestinian group Hamas” though the immediate context was the forceful shutting down of student protest on the Columbia University campus.

Figure 8. August 8, 2024, Columbia University Incident (Screenshot, Cambre)

The issue of the student camps at various universities, the competing accounts and how they were framed, is rooted in the wider societal divisions and how they are supported by constellations of institutional and media messages that often end up obscuring the representation of events as they happen by triggering larger emotionally overlaid narratives. This issue is a serious one, and merits much more space than that available here. Yet, we note the ways in which the triangle is mobilized here, and how the larger narratives are invoked, which are outlined below.

5.2. Historical and cultural aspects

The ▼image directly connects to 1930s and 40s era Nazi death camps, like Auschwitz, where these triangles were sewn or drawn onto prisoner’s clothes to designate reasons for imprisonment. The classification system used triangles of various

colors, with the red used originally as a reference to communists or German Social Democrats, but then expanding to include all political prisoners.

Figure 9. Classification System in Nazi Concentration Camps

At the time, the ▼ image was not explicitly antisemitic since concentration camp badges followed a chromatic schema and any classification of Jewish prisoners had the various triangles overlaid or underlaid by a yellow triangle in the opposing orientation so that one over the other suggested a star of David symbol. Nevertheless, many groups (even some seen as authorities on the subject) have taken up the red inverted triangle as a symbol of hate because of the ways in which some have used it in protest.

Another historical strand locates the ▼ image as a symbol representing Arab liberation because of its presence on the flag of the 1916 Arab Revolt where the king of the Hejaz rose up against the Ottoman Empire, in alliance with the United Kingdom.

Figure 10. Royal Collection Trust/His Majesty King Charles III 2022

Pan-Arab colors of red, white, black and green are found in whole or in part on the flags of Jordan, Kuwait, Egypt, the UAE, Sudan, Syria, and with a particular echo of the

red triangle, Palestine (since 2006), which features the green horizontal stripe at the bottom with the white one in the middle. When the flag is hung the triangle appears inverted and matches the symbol. Extensive research has been done on the provenance and symbolism of the shapes and colors on the flags, as well as on the aforementioned Nazi era use of the triangle shapes. It goes without saying, that countless other red triangle pointing down instances exist, like monuments in different places that feature the image, and other cultural contexts, like the use of the ▼ image to indicate entryways for fire brigades (<https://living.rise-corp.tokyo/red-triangle-on-the-window/>) are also not uncommon. The rich history and competing narratives around this image ground it in social, cultural and political potentiality, and provide a host of directions an analysis might take.

Over the space of 10 months following the use of the red triangle by Al-Qassam Brigades, countless comments on YouTube, Facebook and X, and conducting an interview with the wearer of the red triangle leg tattoo, the as-if of the image is evident in the perpetual oscillation between the material and virtual of the triangle that is used as an artifice to create a parallelism. This parallelism, when recognized by those who have an affinity to, and are following the visual moves being made, acts on them, as recipients and invites responses that cross cultural, political and language boundaries, not to mention spatial and temporal. A Trojan horse for example, was seen as a gift, but for those who knew its contents it was a weapon, “as-if” gift. The gift aspect oscillated between being real and material depending on the way one was viewing the Trojan horse, much like a calligram depends on the perception of the recipient at the moment.

In Figure 11, we have the following “as-if” triangles: In the center there is a triangular piece of pita bread, with the ▼ image superimposed. The group of fighters eating, saw the bread “as-if” triangle and filmed it, sharing it online with other brigades.

Figure 11. Triangle "as-if"s

This was one of the early gestures in summer 2024 whereby the ▼ was not functioning as an arrow in a military context but rather became part of the connective tissue between various Brigades forces. Sometime after the pita bread, the lower right image of fruit arranged so that there would be an equilateral triangle in the center was shared by another group of fighters. In this case, the super-position of the digital red

triangle was no longer necessary, so that it was both there and not there, it was present but not visible. This was understood by the intended recipients, but also by a vast online audience following the visual play. It did not take long for a pizza image, again with a triangle gesture invoking not only the military videos, but also the chain of food images that were creating a sense of solidarity. Why? Because there was a shared phenomenon of seeing various food items “as-if” they were the ▼image, so that the triangle itself figuratively becomes nourishment. It is understood and taken up in a memetic way. Audiences also understood, which led to a sense of desire to participate in using the triangle. At the same time, the fighters began to add the digital triangle to a number of other object images when they were shared online, take the 2 pictures on the left (a notebook outlining an ambush strategy) and a hand showing an Israeli-made bullet that was salvaged, and on the top right a munition that again appears to be salvaged, but is seen by the video producers as a ▼image, despite its being more oblong. Why? Because these are the artefacts that manifest resistance, the “return to sender” ammunition and the plans for an operation, are communicated across groups in a double gesture of both solidarity and resistance.

When I interviewed M. Stainsby, the bearer of the triangle tattoo, only the following questions were asked: 1. Do you recall where and how you first encountered the red triangle, and the context and form of it? 2. What prompted you to learn more about it? 3. Tell me the story of how this came to be a tattoo.

M. Stainsby, ostensibly unaware of some of the uses of the triangle described above, said that he believed it was an arrow in the Al-Qassam Brigades videos, and had seen it extensively used in comment cascades in various media platforms, without knowing much more about it. However, when he was given a triangle sticker at a protest march and in discussion with other participants there, he learned more about the red triangle and its use in communicating “resistance, at the same time as solidarity” (his words describing his reception of the information). In the time that followed, he researched the image, learned much about the political, cultural and social history of the use of this symbol and decided in the end to make it a tattoo. In sharing the image online, he became part of the ocean of triangle images resonating off each other and causing further active or passive responses. The ▼image becomes a medium of participation, as well as a declaration, in this case inked onto skin. Desire functions to have viewers sympathetic to the Palestinian cause, to wish to enter into the experience presented by the red triangle pointing down, that creates a social link between those who use it. The magnitude of the presence and circulation of the ▼image cannot be underestimated. People from around the world communicate with each other by simply posting a string of triangles in a comment thread, no words.

5.3. Nomadic semiotics

At this point, Alfred Gell’s work provides traction in the next move from the semiotic platform to a nomadic non-linear approach. To ground his theory, Gell (1998) expands the notion of index far beyond traditional semiotics by re-framing the notion of cause, while at the same time rejecting much of C.S. Peirce’s semiotic doctrine. The red triangle pointing down is a “modality through which something affects something else” (Gell 1998: 42). As agentic, but relational and context dependent, “whatever type of action a person may perform vis-à-vis another person may be performed also by a work of art, in the realms of imagination if not in reality” (p. 66). Because we recognize agency by its effects, only when someone acts as an agent can they become an agent and not before. They must “disturb the causal milieu in such a way as can only be attributed to their agency” (p. 20). An artifact is rarely a primary agent but can act as a

secondary agent. For example, when a child feeds a doll because it is hungry, the doll is a secondary agent to the degree that it is able to channel or become a conduit for the primary agent's action (p. 26).

While we have identified various starting points, or prototypes (dispositifs) for the image, it circulates in the unmapped spaces of the Internet, emerging into the material world at various points, depending on how people take it up. It always already inhabits a "nomadological" context, that the world is constantly on the move, "without departure or arrival" (Deleuze & Guattari, 1987: 353). While the ephemerality and movement inherent in visual social imagery is widely acknowledged, it seems that much analysis has focused on the static image, or the filmic product, rather than the ways in which the shifts of an image geographically and contextually not only change its perception but accrue and gather weight behind the ways viewers attach significations to it. One of the central themes in the philosophical tour de force by Gilles Deleuze and Felix Guattari (1987), *A Thousand Plateaus* (ATP) they conceive of the nomad not as a Bedouin-like wanderer, but rather as a latent state of being that tends toward subjective liberation from standardized institutional ways of thinking and acting. The process critical to the release of creative energies, deterritorialization, is possible when unexamined paradigmatic assumptions suddenly come into view.

6. Conclusion

What might analysis that thinks "by," "on," and "through" images entail? It might include the production of images as analysis, the curation and placing of images together as another possible layer, an examination of the contexts of use, and the ways in which images might relate to each other at or across any particular discourse. As such, image analysis within sociological work necessarily pushes past looking simply at the atomistic contents of any particular picture or series. Conversely, attending mostly to networks of production and the political economy of images while bypassing what is depicted in the images themselves is also limiting. If "pictures provide insights into the practices through which people construct themselves as social beings within specific locales and enable us to link personal life worlds to wider societal contexts" (Hodgetts *et al.*, 2007: 267) we can ground an analysis of the deep complexities associated with using visual images, without ignoring affective and aesthetic levels. Thus, images transversally manifest intersections of power, subjectivity and agency where power relations weigh heavily on what might be considered its contents, and how it will be taken up for its social meaning.

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